

Relationship between Green Human Resource Management and Individual performance as Non Environmental factor: A study on commercial banks in Bangladesh

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Abstract:

The concept of green HRM was appeared in 1990s and globally accepted in 2000s. Like others organization, commercial banks in Bangladesh have also adopted green HRM. In today's competitive business situation, organizations want to see bottom line result of their initiatives. Though Green HRM sounds an environmental issue, it may also have association with non environmental factors. The core objective of this paper is to investigate that assumption. Employees of commercial banks operating in Bangladesh were the population of the study. For the purpose of the study, author selected a sample size of 100 employees with the technique of convenient random sampling and collected data through a self-administrative questionnaire. The paper deployed both online and field survey to collect primary data. Responses were measured with Likert 5 point scales ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. To attain the research objectives, author applied nonparametric test including Mann-Whitney U test, Spearman's rho and Kendall's tau_b Correlation and descriptive statistics with SPSS 22. Descriptive statistics evinces that commercial banks are practicing green HRM (mean=3.84, SD=. 35) while result of Mann-Whitney U test indicates ($U=459.0$, $p=.000$) that public commercial banks and private commercial banks differ in green HRM implementation. Private commercial banks are implementing more green policy in comparison to public commercial banks. Result of Spearman's rho and Kendall's tau_b Correlation confirm that green HRM has positive strong association with individual performance including task performance and productive behavior and the relation is significant. Moreover, the study found weak relation of green HRM with contextual performance but the relation is not statistically significant. Finally, the paper recommended that there is a huge room for improvement in implementing green HRM by public commercial banks and more empirical research with robust statistical analysis is the demand of time to get more insight about green HRM in Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

The world class experts are talking and thinking about a number of critical issues in the 21st century and Climate change is one of them. From the work of Victor (2001), Al Mamun (2019) opined that the global warming which is direct result of greenhouse gas emissions is not only a matter of concern but also a colossal challenge for human being to protect the earth and sustain it as suitable for living by reducing climate change. Therefore environmental sustainability is becoming a matter of concern among business executives, governments, consumers, management scholars and other entities (Mehta & Chugan, 2015). Though the reasons of climate change are numerous, augmentation of industrialization, immense scale of production, and quick establishment of relevant supporting entity of industrialization are bringing fundamental change to the world climate (Grenville et al. 2014). The last three decades experienced unbroken movement to industrialization with advantages like employment, innovative process, exploration of new product, and overall better service for the society (Arun, 2020). To address the problem of sustainability and elimination of environmental hazards which are associated with industrialization, Mathapati (2013) opined that integration of environmental management into Human Resource Management is the demand of 21st Century to mitigate burning issues like ecological imbalances and the bio-diversity.

Banking industry is playing vital role in Bangladesh economy. Banks are also contributing a lot to Bangladesh to be a developed country by 2041 by rendering funds to public and private sector and accelerating major drivers of economic growth (Khuda, 2019). Besides economic contribution Banking sector of Bangladesh is paying attention to the environmental sustainability (Zhixia et al., 2018). Integration of environment management and Human Resource Management is becoming a vital business strategy for modern organizations in which Human Resource Department play major roles to make workplace green and augment green practice awareness among the employees. The same strategy when applied to banking sector is known as green banking. "Green Banking is an umbrella term used for practices and guidelines that make banks sustainable in economic, environment and social dimensions"(Sunita & Sharma, 2017). The locomotion of the world toward Green Banking also has influenced the Human Resource Department of banks in Bangladesh to adopt green policy and procedure in Human Resource Functions. They count for environment and sustainability when involve in recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation, performance appraisal, working condition, employee involvement and so on (Islam, 2017).

Though Green HRM mainly imply environment-friendly HR actions to promote sustainability, it also affects costs, operation, marketing, financial performance, employee commitments, employee engagement, retention, morality, work life balance and employee satisfaction (Halawi & Zaraket, 2018; O'Donohue & Torugsa, 2016; and Tulasi Das & Sreedhar Reddy, 2016). On the other hand the overall success of an organization depends largely on employee performance (Leonard, 2019). Employee performance is critical and it is associated with compensation, reward, promotion, demotion, training decision and so on. Therefore, it is significant for the authority to understand individual performance to control task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior of bank employees. However, the scope of this paper is to assess employee awareness of Green Human Resource Management practice and its relation with individual work performance of commercial banks employees in Bangladesh.

1.1 Research objectives

The core objective of the paper is to explore green HRM practice in banking sector of Bangladesh and association of green HRM with non environmental issues. To attain the core objectives, some specific objective would be addressed. First of all, this paper will assess the level to which commercial banks practice green HRM (Green recruitment and selection, Green performance management, Green pay and reward, Green involvement and workplace, Green training) in Bangladesh. Secondly, the author will explore if public and private commercial banks differ in practicing green HRM significantly in Bangladesh. Last but not the least; the paper will explore the relationship between green HRM and individual performance (task and contextual performance and productive behavior) of commercial banks.

2. Literature Review

Literature review is a systematic evaluation of previous studies to form a theoretical basis which helps determine the research philosophy, research gape, methods to be deployed and so on. A literature review involves searching for information, identification and articulation of relationships between the previous study and field of research (Sunita et al., 2017).

2.1 Related theoretical concept

Green Human Resource Management

The concept of GHRM was appeared in 1990s and globally accepted in 2000s Lee (2009) as mentioned by Krithika et al., (2019) and they defined "Green HRM is the implication of green HRM policies, green philosophies and green practices for the environmental management and awareness among the employees about green environmental responsibilities". On the other hand Opatha and Arulrajah (2014) defined Green HRM as all the activities involved in development, implementation and continuous maintenance of a system that try to make employees adaptable to green. They also added that green HRM which is concerned with transforming employees and turning them into green employees helps organization to achieve environmental goals as well as environmental sustainability. Mampra (2013) defines Green HRM as the use of HRM policies to encourage and promote the sustainable use of organizational resources to augment employee morale and satisfaction. But Zoogah (2011) opined that Green HRM is the combined application of HRM policies, philosophies, and practices to promote sustainable use of business resources and avoid any unwanted harm arising from environment from the business operations (Ahmad, 2015). From the definition of others, Green HRM covers a broaden area and refers to the policies, practices and systems that make employees of the organization green for the benefit of all including the individual, society, environment, and the business as a whole.

To be green, a green organization develops HRM functions according to the Green HRM practices and policies to attain both sustainability and reflecting 'Eco-focuses (Krithika et al., 2019). The GHRM functions include GHR planning, Green recruitment & selection, Green Training & development, Green Performance management system (PMS), Green compensation and benefits, Green involvement (Renwick et al., 2008; and Tang et al., 2018).

Employee Performance

Employee performance is regarded as the backbone of an organization on the ground that it directly influences the core part of the organization such as productivity and profit (Teoh et al., 2021). Employee performance is the behavior of employees which negatively or positively contribute to an organization Colquitt et al., (2018) and help achieve organizational goals (Campbell, 1990). Employee performance is behavior at workplace that can be assessed in terms of quality and quantity (Shahzadi et al., 2014). Leadership style and Organizational

culture (Diana et al., 2021), education, training, and work experience (Santi, 2020), job stress, motivation, and communication (Muda et al., 2014) are some of many factors that influence performance. Borman & Motowidlo, (1993) opined that two factors mainly consist in work performance and those are Task performance and Contextual performance (Markus, 2019). Task performances are the core responsibility and outcome that can be expressed in quality and quantity. On the other hand, Contextual performances are those activities which employee contribute spontaneously and not as a part of regular job (Koopmans et al., 2014).

Counterproductive Behavior as opposite to productive Behavior

Counterproductive behaviors are employee behavior that goes beyond the general rules of the organization and resist organization to attain its goals (Jex, 2002). Tardiness, absenteeism, gossiping, gambling, rumors and misuses of organizational resources are some types of behavior that leads to less effective employee performance in the organization (Jay and Ateneo, 2016). Therefore, productive Behavior is those attitudes of employees, directly or indirectly expected by the organization. Productive Behavior is informal but highly influencer of employee performance. Organization to be competitive and get success must develop and maintain a pool of talents with behavior that support the productivity of the organization.

2.2 Empirical study

Though Green HRM is an emerging and promising field, very few studies have been conducted to explore the awareness level of employees in the field of Green human resource management in Bangladesh. Al Mamun (2019) conducted a research to identify the awareness level on Green HRM in Bangladesh. The author included different sectors in the study and on the basis of research findings recommended that organizations should practice Green HRM to achieve excellent organizational performance. On the other hand, before the study of Mamun (2019), a study was conducted by Zhixia et al., (2018) to explore the implementation of Green HRM in banking industry of Bangladesh. As a source of study materials, the authors deployed annual reports of the Central Bank of Bangladesh, review report of green banking and so on. On the basis of content analysis, the paper found that Bangladeshi banks are practicing Green banking accordance with standardized guideline provided by Bangladesh Bank along with their own policies. Chowdhury and Singha (2012) reviewed the studies on Green Banking in Bangladesh to Foster Environmentally Sustainable Inclusive Growth Process and they found that Bangladesh is encouraging low-carbon green development in banking sector. But Ullah (2013) compared between state-owned commercial banks and private commercial banks and found that private commercial banks have adopted more green banking initiatives in Bangladesh.

The results of research evinces that Green HRM such as green recruitment, green training, green learning influence organizational performance (Obaid & Alias, 2015) as well as financial performance (O'Donohue & Torugsa, 2016). In Sri Lanka, Shaumya and Arulrajah (2017) conducted a research on 155 bank employees to measure the impact of Green HRM practice in bank on environmental performance. With univariate, bivariate and multivariate analyses, the study found significant relationship between Green HRM and environmental performance of the bank. Mohan et al., (2020) studied 324 samples from pharmaceutical companies in Hyderabad city to understand relationship between GHRM and professional engagement. From Pearson correlation and step-wise multiple regression, the authors concluded that there is significant correlation among Green HRM practices (G recruitment and selection, G training, G performance management, G pay and reward and G involvement) and work engagement. John and Sathiq (2018) studied scheduled banks in India with a sample size of 172 and research result evinces that majority of the respondent knows the

concept of Green HRM. The researchers concluded that employees in banks having Green HRM practice experienced high level job satisfaction and the rate vary from banks to banks and the degree to which banks involves in Green practice.

Dumont et al., (2016) assumed from literature that there is an influential relation between green HRM and employee green workplace behavior. To verify that assumption, the authors developed measures and conducted a study on 390 employees of a Chinese subsidiary. After a rigorous analysis (exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis and so on) on the data, the study concluded that “*green HRM both directly and indirectly influenced in-role (Task performance) green behavior, but only indirectly influenced extra-role (contextual behavior) green behavior*”. Finally, the authors provided future research direction and recommended to focus on different work setting, culture, time duration, and subject matter such as the future research may be conducted to explore the impact of green HRM on factors beyond employee green behavior including sustainability, short and long term goals, job satisfaction, individual performance and motivation.

2.3 Research Gap and Rationality of the Study

From the literature on green HRM, both theory and empirical, it is clear that research in the field of green HRM has got huge attraction in Bangladesh (Rimi, 2016). Especially in banking sector, demand for green banking has increased rapidly from past few years (Balo & Hossain, 2018). But most of the paper explored the degree to which green HRM is being implemented and organizations are conscientious about green HRM and the matter is clear from the contribution of (Chowdhury and Singha, 2012; Ullah, 2013; Zhixia et al., 2018; and Al Mamun, 2019). The green HRM generally associated with environment but it may have influence on others organizational factions such as workplace behavior, employee morale, productivity, performance, organizational long term goals, cost and profit margin. Considerable numbers of scholars conducted research at abroad to examine the causal relationship between green HRM and organizational performance (Obaid & Alias, 2015), financial performance (O'Donohue & Torugsa, 2016), environmental performance (Shaumya and Arulrajah, 2017), work engagement (Mohan et al., 2020), job satisfaction (John and Sathiq 2018) and workplace behavior (Dumont et al., 2016). So there is a research gap and relationship between or impact of green HRM on non environmental issue such as job satisfaction, motivation and employee performance can be explored. Moreover, very few research in the field of green HRM have been done in Bangladesh due to researchers negligence (Mamun, 2019). Therefore, it is rational to conduct research to assess the degree to which employees of banking industry are known to green HRM and how implementation of green HRM in banks influence the individual performance(task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior) of commercial banks in Bangladesh. The findings of this paper may contribute to the existing green HRM literature greatly and enrich effective green HRM practice in Bangladeshi banks as recommended by (Zhixia et al., 2018). Moreover, authority may get some hints to improve employee performance through more involvement in green HRM.

3. Conceptual Framework

The Figure:1 is showing 5 independent variables under green HRM and one dependent variable employee performance (task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior). Campbell et al., (2015) opined that “Individual work role performance drives the entire economy” and work performance is the most crucial dependent variable in an organization from the view point of organizational psychology and organizational behavior.

That's why the scholars say organizational success is the outcome of employee performance as studied by (Siddiqui, 2014). However, the notion of this paper is to see either green HRM (independent variable), including Green recruitment and selection (GRS), Green performance management (GPM), Green training (GT), Green pay and reward (GPR), & Green involvement (GI) (Tang et al., 2018), has significant relationship with non environmental issues (dependent variable) of banks. The author of the papers has taken employee performance (task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior) as dependent variable for the study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the study

The locomotion of the conceptual framework is that green HRM may have association with task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior. If so happens, there would be an effect on individual employee performance result in organizational goals achievement. Moreover, the organization will be more interested in implementing green HRM if they find evidence that green HRM has relation with non environmental issues too besides environmental issues.

4. Methodology of the study

This is a quantitative research which had been conducted to explore the relationship of green HRM with non environmental issues- employee performance of banking industry of Bangladesh. Both primary and secondary data were utilized to complete the study. The author collected secondary data from newspapers, websites, and mostly from published journals. The population of the study was employees of public and private commercial banks operating in Bangladesh. From the population, the author selected 100 samples on the basis of convenient sampling method. The researcher collected Primary data from the target group using a self-administered structured questionnaire. A Google drive form was created and administrated through Gmail and face book messenger for the purpose. Beside considerable amount (46%) of primary data was collected through field survey from Mymensingh city. To assess the green HRM practice from the view point of employees, the paper developed green HRM tools including Green recruitment and selection (GRS), Green performance management (GPM), Green training (GT), Green pay and reward (GPR), & Green involvement (GI) from the tools of (Tang et al., 2018) and to assess performance of employees the tools including task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior of (Koopmans et al., 2014) was deployed. Some question was rewritten to match circumstance. To measure productive

behavior, the questions of counterproductive behavior were reversed. For example, in counterproductive behavior the question was “I complained about unimportant matters at work” but it has been written as I don’t complain about unimportant matters at work. Questions were measured with 5 points Likert scales ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The paper deployed Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk test to verify the normality of data distribution, on the basis of which nonparametric test were done to reach research objectives. Mean and standard deviation were calculated to assess the level to which commercial banks practice green HRM. Author applied Mann-Whitney U test to assess if public and private commercial banks differ in practicing green HRM. To explore the relationship between green HRM and individual employee performance, author deployed both Spearman’s rho and Kendall's tau_b Correlation. All the statistical test and tabulation was done with the help of SPSS version 22.

5. Results

5.1 Demographic Analysis of the Respondents

Table 1 shows that, (n=100, 52%) of the respondents are from public commercial banks and (n=1000, 48%) are from private commercial banks. In term of demography gender, the study comprises (n=100, 74%) male respondents and the rest part of the respondents (n=100, 26%) are female.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Respondents

Demographic Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Type of commercial Banks (n=100)			
Public commercial Banks	52	52	52
Private commercial Banks	48	48	100
Gender (n=100)			
Male	74	74	74
Female	26	26	100
Age of the Respondents(n=100)			
Less than 30 years	59	59	59
31-40 years	31	31	90
41-50 years	10	10	100
Education & professional Degree(n=100)			
Honors or equivalent	01	01	01
Masters or equivalent	82	82	83
Both Masters and diploma	17	17	100
Designation (n=100)			
Assistance Officer	20	20	20
Officer	50	50	70
Principal Officer	08	08	78
Senior Officer	22	22	100
Duration in the job (n=100)			
1 to 3 years	68	68	68
4 to 7 years	23	23	91
8 to 15 years	09	09	100

Source: Survey data analysis

The study has collected data from different aged group randomly and the age of the respondents are as follows, less than 30 years are (n=100, 59%), age ranged from 31-40 years are (n=100, 31%) and aged ranged from 41-50 years are (n=100, 10%). The table also represents the education & professional degree of the respondents. Among the respondents (n=100, 82%) have masters or equivalent degree and (n=100, 17%) respondents have completed professional degree beside formal education. The study collected data from

different level to reflect the real scenario of green HRM and the demography regarding position, the study comprises (n=100, 20%) assistant officer, (n=100, 50%) are officer, (n=100, 08%) principal officer and rest (n=100, 22%) are senior officer. Finally the table depicts the demographics regarding years in the job. The largest portion of the respondents (n=100, 68%) have experience between 1 to 3 years while (n=100, 23%) falls between 4 to 7 years and rest part of the respondents (n=100, 09%) have between 8 to 15 years of job experience.

5.2 Test of Normality of Data Distribution

Table 2 shows the result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk test to verify the normality of data distribution by assuming data are normally distributed. For the results to be valid, some statistical tests are applied to analyze data and to ensure that the data meet required assumptions (Tsagris and Pandis, 2021). Again test of normality is important to select appropriate statistical methods for data analysis. When the data follows a normal distribution, parametric tests are applied. On the other hand, non normal data requires nonparametric test (Mishra et al., 2019). The table presents that Green HRM ($p < .05$), Green Recruitment & selection ($p < .05$), Green Training ($p < .05$), Green performance management ($p < .05$), Green pay & reward ($p < .05$), Green involvement and workplace ($p < .05$), Individual Performance ($p < .05$), Task Performance ($p < .05$), Contextual Performance ($p < .05$) and Productive Behavior ($p < .05$) do not support to retain the null hypothesis of normality. So on the basis of both Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk test, the author concludes that the data in this paper is not normally distributed and nonparametric test would be appropriate. Therefore, nonparametric test including Mann-Whitney U (Wilcoxon W), Spearman's rho and Kendall's tau_b Correlation would be applied to reach at the objectives of the study.

Study Variables	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Green HRM	.142	100	.000	.965	100	.009
Green Recruitment & selection	.224	100	.000	.872	100	.000
Green Training	.228	100	.000	.890	100	.000
Green performance management	.212	100	.000	.927	100	.000
Green pay & reward	.209	100	.000	.901	100	.000
Green involvement and workplace	.217	100	.000	.924	100	.000
Individual Performance	.145	100	.000	.923	100	.000
Task Performance	.259	100	.000	.884	100	.000
Contextual Performance	.153	100	.000	.892	100	.000
Productive Behavior	.264	100	.000	.773	100	.000

Source: SPSS 22 output from survey data

5.3 Green HRM practice by commercial banks in Bangladesh

The table 3 is presenting the responses of 100 samples from commercial banks in Bangladesh. According to the perception of the respondents, commercial banks are implementing green HRM with $\bar{x}=3.84$ which is greater than neutral situation with Std. Deviation .35. The respondents agree that commercial banks involve in green training ($\bar{x}=4.21$, $SD=.319$) and Green involvement and workplace ($\bar{x}=4.86$, $SD=.293$). Employees agree that commercial banks practice Green Recruitment & selection ($(\bar{x}=3.86-SD=.499) = 3.37$). On the other hand, Green performance management ($\bar{x}=3.65$, $SD=.699$) and Green pay & reward ($\bar{x}=3.41$, $SD=.76$) falls between the range of neutral and agree which indicate clear room for improvement.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Green HRM	100	3.05	4.82	3.84	.356
Green Recruitment & selection	100	2.66	5.00	3.86	.499
Green Training	100	3.67	5.00	4.21	.319
Green performance management	100	2.00	5.00	3.65	.699
Green pay & reward	100	1.33	4.67	3.41	.761
Green involvement and workplace	100	3.29	4.86	4.06	.293
Valid N (listwise)	100				

Source: SPSS 22 output from survey data

5.4 Difference of public and private commercial banks in Green HRM practice

A Mann-Whitney U test has been carried out on 100 samples of the study to find out if public and private commercial banks practice green HRM equally. As the sample size is greater than 30, z test has been done. Table 4 shows the calculated z-values and statistical significance difference between public and private commercial banks in practicing green HRM. For every variable, z-value has a negative figure. However, this is very common in a two-sample test to have z negative figure which indicates the second group has greater values than the first group (*Salvatore S.2019*). In this study the first group is public commercial bank and second group is private commercial banks with greater values in practicing green HRM.

	Green HRM	Green Recruitment & selection	Green Training	Green performance management	Green pay & reward	Green involvement and workplace
Mann-Whitney U	459.000	1023.500	443.000	720.500	573.500	651.000
Wilcoxon W	1837.00	2401.500	1821.000	2098.500	1951.500	2029.000
Z	-5.460	-1.607	-5.871	-3.739	-4.729	-4.228
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.108	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Grouping Variable: Public and private commercial Banks

Source: Survey data calculation

Mann-Whitney U test indicates that green HRM (U=459.0, p=.000), Green Training (U=443.000, p=.000), Green performance management (U=720.500, p=.000), Green pay & reward (U=573.500, p=.000), Green involvement and workplace (U=651, p=.000) practice are greater for private commercial banks comparing to public commercial banks which is statistically significant. But the test indicates that private and public commercial banks do not significantly differ in practicing green recruitment and selection (U=1023.500, p=.108). Mean rank of each group can provide information about how much a given group tends to have high values (Alberti, 2017). Therefore, the extent, to which the value of private commercial banks is higher than those of public commercial banks, has been presented with mean ranks. Table 5 shows that private commercial banks mostly implement (as perceived by employees) Green Training (Mean Rank=67.27) followed by Green pay & reward (Mean Rank=64.55), Green involvement and workplace (Mean Rank=62.94), Green performance management (Mean

Rank=61.49) and Green Recruitment & selection (Mean Rank=55.18). The table 5 also conveys that public commercial banks have lower mean ranks regarding all green HRM variables comparing to private commercial banks. Moreover, Mann whitney U test indicates that private and public commercial banks do not significantly differ in practicing green recruitment and selection ($U=1023.500$, $p=.108$) but mean ranks evinces that private banks has greater mean rank value (55.18) comparing to public commercial banks (46.18). So, private commercial banks involve more in green HRM practice comparing to public commercial banks in Bangladesh.

	Type of Banks	N	Mean Rank
Green Recruitment & selection	Public Bank	52	46.18
	Private Bank	48	55.18
	Total	100	
Green Training	Public Bank	52	35.02
	Private Bank	48	67.27
	Total	100	
Green performance management	Public Bank	52	40.36
	Private Bank	48	61.49
	Total	100	
Green pay & reward	Public Bank	52	37.53
	Private Bank	48	64.55
	Total	100	
Green involvement and workplace	Public Bank	52	39.02
	Private Bank	48	62.94
	Total	100	

Source: Survey data calculation

5.5 Relationship between green HRM and individual performance

Spearman's rho Correlation was run to explore the association between green HRM and individual performance including task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior. In table 6, horizontal line presents individual performance including its sub variables and vertical line is presenting green HRM variables as well as green HRM. According to the table, Green Recruitment & selection has positive association ($r_s=.319$) with Individual employee Performance which is statistically significant with p value 0.001. But Green Recruitment & selection has not found to be significantly associated with Task Performance, Contextual Performance and Productive Behavior. Green Training has weak relationship with Task Performance and moderate level relationship with Contextual Performance and Productive Behavior but the relationship is significant with p value .000. Again, Green Training has positive association ($r_s=.379$) with Individual employee Performance which is statistically significant ($p=.000$). Green Performance management is significantly associated ($r_s=.448$), ($r_s=.281$), ($r_s=.489$), and ($r_s=.523$) with Task Performance, Contextual Performance, Productive Behavior and Individual Performance respectively. Moreover, Green Pay & Rewards ($r_s=.495$, $p=.000$) and Green Involvement & workplace ($r_s=.272$, $p=.006$) have significant relationship with Individual Performance including Task Performance, Contextual Performance and Productive Behavior. Finally Spearman's rho Correlation evince that Green HRM has been found to have significant positive correlation with Individual Performance ($r_s=.567$, $p=.000$), Task Performance ($r_s=.519$, $p=.000$), and Productive Behavior ($r_s=.444$, $p=.000$).

Table:6 Spearman’s rho Correlation

Green HRM Variables			Task Performance	Contextual Performance	Productive Behavior	Individual Performance
Green Recruitment & selection		Correlation coefficient	.181	.084	.155	.319**
		Sig.(2-tailed) (N=100)	.072	.408	.124	.001
Green Training		Correlation coefficient	.245*	.481**	.488**	.379**
		Sig.(2-tailed) (N=100)	.000	.000	.000	.000
Green Performance management		Correlation Coefficient	.448**	.281*	.489**	.523**
		Sig. (2-tailed) (N=100)	.000	.013	.000	.000
Green Pay & Rewards		Correlation Coefficient	.520**	.114	.331**	.495**
		Sig. (2-tailed) (N=100)	.000	.260	.001	.000
Green Involvement & workplace		Correlation Coefficient	.246*	.116	.219*	.272**
		Sig. (2-tailed) (N=100)	.014	.251	.028	.006
Green HRM		Correlation coefficient	.519**	.193	.444**	.567**
		Sig.(2-tailed) (N=100)	.000	.054	.000	.000

Source: Survey data analysis in SPSS 22

Table:7 Kendall's tau_b Correlation

Green HRM Variables			Task Performance	Contextual Performance	Productive Behavior	Individual Performance
Green Recruitment & selection		Correlation coefficient	.132	.096	.132	.258**
		Sig.(2-tailed) (N=100)	.105	.232	.118	.001
Green Training		Correlation coefficient	.212*	.401**	.318**	.692**
		Sig.(2-tailed) (N=100)	.010	.000	.000	.000
Green Performance management		Correlation Coefficient	.400**	.192*	.379**	.438**
		Sig. (2-tailed) (N=100)	.000	.014	.000	.000
Green Pay & Rewards		Correlation Coefficient	.450**	.069	.297**	.431**
		Sig. (2-tailed) (N=100)	.000	.371	.000	.000
Green Involvement & workplace		Correlation Coefficient	.192*	.081	.202*	.206**
		Sig. (2-tailed) (N=100)	.016	.301	.015	.006
Green HRM		Correlation coefficient	.430**	.127	.378**	.474**
		Sig.(2-tailed) (N=100)	.000	.089	.000	.000

Source: Survey data analysis in SPSS 22

The paper deployed Kendall's tau b Correlation besides Spearman's rho Correlation to verify the accuracy of the result. According to the decision roles as opined by (Mastrothanas, 2020), Green Recruitment & selection ($Tb=.258$, $p=001$), Green Training ($Tb=.692$, $p=000$), Green Performance management ($Tb=.438$, $p=000$), Green Pay & Rewards ($Tb=.431$, $p=000$) and overall scale Green HRM ($Tb=.474$, $p=000$) have strong positive association with Individual Performance and the monotonous relationship is statistically significant. Table 7 also shows that among the green HRM variables Green Involvement & workplace ($Tb=.206$, $p=006$) has moderate positive relationship with individual performance.

Finally, the paper found an affinity between the result of Spearman's rho and that of Kendall's tau b. On the basis of the result, the author can conclude that there is a significant monotonous relationship between green HRM variables and individual performance including task performance, contextual performance and productive behavior with two exceptions. Green HRM ($Tb=.127$, $p=089$) and ($r_s=.193$, $p=.054$) found to have weak positive relation with Contextual Performance and Green Recruitment & selection found to have weak association with performance, contextual performance and productive behavior but the relationship is not statistically significant.

6. Discussion with the findings

Green Human Resource Management is an emerging aspect of modern organization. Organizations are implementing green HR policy mostly to address environmental issues and to augment sustainability in business operation. Commercial banks in Bangladesh have also adopted green policy in their operations. The relation of green HRM with environmental issues and sustainability has been clarified with many empirical studies but green HRM may be sensitive to non environmental factors of the organization. The objectives of this paper was to explore this relationship in the context of commercial banks operating in Bangladesh taking individual performance as non environmental factor of the study.

The first objective of the paper was to assess the degree to which commercial banks in Bangladesh are practicing green HRM. Descriptive statistics evince that commercial banks in Bangladesh had adopted green HRM policies ($\bar{x}=3.84$) in their operations. The finding has affinity with the findings of (Zhixia et al., 2018) who conducted the research based on secondary data. On the other hand, this paper is based on employee perception- How the employees have observed the degree to which green HRM is being implemented in banking sector of Bangladesh?. In addition, this paper has found that there is a room for improvement in the arena of Green performance management ($\bar{x}=3.65$) and Green pay & reward ($\bar{x}=3.41$). The analysis indicates that banks emphasise Green Training ($\bar{x}=4.21$) followed by Green involvement and workplace ($\bar{x}=4.06$) and Green Recruitment & selection ($\bar{x}=3.86$) which sounds good enough but a little more care in the area of Green performance management and Green pay & reward can bring additional benefit of implementing green HRM.

The second objective of this paper was to find out if there any difference between public and private commercial banks in practicing green HRM. To achieve the objective, the author run Mann-Whitney U test. Result of Mann-Whitney U test evinces that private commercial banks involve more in practicing green HRM (Green Training, Green performance management, Green pay & reward and Green involvement and workplace) in comparison to public commercial banks and the difference is statistically significant. The finding has similarity with the finding of (Ullah, 2013) who concluded that private commercial banks have adopted more green banking initiatives in Bangladesh. However, this paper has not found any significant difference between public and private commercial banks in green recruitment and selection ($U=1023.500$, $p=.108$). Though the difference is not significant, there is still now

difference. Mean Ranks analysis conveys that public commercial banks have mean ranks of 46.18 where mean ranks of private commercial banks is 55.18. So, public commercial banks have lagged behind in practicing green HRM in all aspect comparing to private commercial banks. Therefore, it is high time that the authority of public commercial banks recognized the value of green practice and involved more in green HRM to address environmental and non environmental issues associated with green HRM.

The last but core objective of the study was to assess the association between green HRM practice and individual performance of commercial banks in Bangladesh. This paper deployed both Kendall's tau b Correlation and Spearman's rho Correlation to ensure accuracy of the result. Both tests provide evidence that green HRM including Green Recruitment & selection, Green Training, Green Performance management, Green Pay & Rewards and Green Involvement & workplace have positive significant relationship with individual performance. According to the range recommended by (Mastrothanasis, 2020), Green Recruitment & selection ($T_b=0.258$, $p=0.001$) and Green Involvement & workplace ($T_b=0.206$, $p=0.006$) has moderate positive relationship with individual performance and all others factors of the study have strong positive association with Individual Performance and the monotonous relationship is statistically significant. That means improvement in green HRM will also improve individual performance because of a monotonous positive association between the dependent (green HRM) and independent variable (individual performance). Though this paper found relationship between green HRM and Individual Performance including Task Performance and Productive Behavior, no significant relation was observed between green HRM and Contextual Performance. More intense investigation is important to reveal the matter.

7. Conclusion

Every organization uses natural resources. But due to day to day business operation, organizations negatively influence the nature. With a view to mitigating this influence, green HRM has emerged and being implemented worldwide. On the other hand, organizations expect bottom line result of any investment. Therefore, to encourage organization to implement green HRM, it is vital to make sense that green HRM not only associated with environmental factors but also have relation with non-environmental issues. This was the notion of this paper in the context of commercial banks in Bangladesh. Results of this paper evince that commercial banks practice green HRM but there is a room for improvement. In comparison to private commercial banks, public commercial banks are not implementing green HRM so that it can be appreciated. To be competitive and responsive to environment, public commercial banks should take more green HRM initiatives. Moreover, this paper has found positive relationship of green HRM with individual performance which indicates that green HRM does not address environmental issues only. Organizations can consider implementing green HRM for non-environmental factors too. However, to generalize the findings of this paper, more research with robust statistical analysis is necessary. Same type of study in different organization with large sample size may provide more insight into the matter. In fine, in order to reap countless benefit of green HRM, such as effectiveness and efficiency in employee performance, reduced production cost, health and safety, high level of employee engagement and motivation, organizations should adopt and practice green HRM to address both environmental and non-environmental factors.

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